

Determinants of Fraud Prevention of Listed Deposit Money Banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 15 July 2024	Background: The study titled the determinants of fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria with the independent variable as forensic investigation services and forensic litigation support services while the dependent variable as fraud prevention. Methodology: The survey research design which made use of primary data drawn from five-point likert scale structured closed-ended questionnaire of fifteen listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The theories in which this study pinned on were profession theory and fraud diamond theory. The SPSS version 25 software statistical package was used for coding of the questionnaire respondents and panel ordinary least square for the study. The multiple regression model was adopted in determining the extent of the effect of independent variable (forensic investigation services & forensic litigation services) on dependent variable (fraud prevention) of the banks under consideration. Results: The result of the regression analysis revealed that forensic investigation services and forensic litigation support services have negative and insignificant effect on fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The implication of the result is that any unit increase in the services of forensic investigation and litigation support will result to a unit decrease on fraud prevention and vice versa. Recommendations: Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that the management should increase the use of forensic investigation services to help reduce the fraudulent activities being committed in the banking sector in Nigeria. Also, the government should provide more evidence strategies (documental, oral, digital etc.) to help support litigation activities been presented in the court by the forensic accountants.
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KEYWORDS: fraud prevention, forensic investigation services, forensic litigation support services, multiple regression and SPSS.	

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past few decades, forensic has become vital not only for policy makers but also for all the users of information to ensure, the trust of different stakeholder groups beyond the stockholders is critical. During the administration of Nigerian President Buhari in 2015, it was indicated that the priority of his administration would be to fight against corruption so as to drastically reduce the cases of financial malpractice (Ismail, 2020; Enofe et al, 2017). Fraud is a cancerous menace that affects every nation's growth and development, and it shouldn't be understated on a worldwide scale. That is one of the factors that make forensic accounting essential in

the fight against fraud in the Nigerian public sector (Enofe et al., 2015).

Today, fraud prevention should not only be a necessity but also a smart business practice for the majority of businesses that are exposed to several hazards, all of which have enormous potential for harm. Of these dangers, legal causation is particularly noteworthy for corporations and other entities that have been held accountable for criminal conduct carried out as a result of organizational policy for criminal activities done by employees while they are employed and for the profit of the corporate entity, subjecting the organization to liability as well. On occasion, a worker

will act improperly on the company's behalf, putting the company in jeopardy (Shewangu, 2015).

Recently, businesses around the world have faced challenges in growing their businesses, including revenue generation and community activities to better the environment (Nnamani et al., 2017). Firms' solvency or insolvency is apparent based on how they respond to their forensic reporting. Forensic reporting should not only be viewed as a public relations tool but also as a tool that can assist businesses in recognizing their strengths and weaknesses and certain interdependencies within them (Ionica et al., 2020). Managers have the ability to present good or bad news through accounting disclosures as well as other disclosures and announcements, which may have an impact on the accuracy of financial reporting. If competitors knew about the information, it would give them an advantage. Managers are required to submit both positive and negative information without any bias during the reporting period. Managers exaggerate incomes in difficult times to keep their jobs or cut earnings in prosperous times to avoid difficult periods in the future (Nwaiwu et al, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

It is believed that forensic accounting developed in reaction to several newly emerging fraud-related situations, such as the ENRON and WorldCom scandals, which startled the world and highlighted corporate dishonesty and greed that are ingrained in human brains. The recent financial scandals that occurred in the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) for over N2.6 billion in school feeding scandals in Federal Government Schools, the Ministry of Education scandals, and the Chairman of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) Scandals (Ismail, 2020)

The increase in corporate crimes and auditors' failure to detect and decrease fund misappropriation have put pressure on professional accountants and attorneys to find a more effective strategy to expose these crimes to the broader public, and the issue is that constant criminal activity in the business environment necessitates routine audits. In order to gather enough evidence for use in court processes, forensic auditing should be in charge of locating frauds that were perpetrated through the use of auditing, accounting, and investigative techniques (Ehioghren & Atu, 2016). Although a number of studies have been done on the concept of forensic accounting, none of them have focused on the determinants of fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in Abuja, FCT, Nigeria, using two variables such as forensic investigation services, forensic litigation support services as independent variable and fraud prevention as dependent variable. In light of the above problems and more, it becomes necessary to evaluate the determinants of fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in Abuja, FCT, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Forensic Investigation Services

Edward (2021) defined forensic investigation services as an examination which uses a scientific approach or another skill, like finance or assessment knowledge, and searches backward to reach a decision regarding an event that took place previously.

Okoye, et al (2020) described forensic investigation services as the use of investigative and analytical techniques to address financial difficulties in a way that satisfies legal criteria is another way to define forensic inquiry. The process of using science to produce facts or evidence that will be utilized in criminal trials or other legal proceedings is known as forensic inquiry. An investigation is a thorough or comprehensive examination conducted to find out the truth. It is a critical aspect of forensic accounting and auditing procedure but only employed when the event or transaction is beclouded. It is carried out when lapse has been proved to discover who is accountable for the damage in the organization.

2.1.2 Forensic Litigation Support Services

The interpretation and depiction of issues that are related to supporting ongoing or impending litigation are taken into consideration by forensic litigation support services. In this area of expertise, the forensic accountant may be asked to assign a hypothetical value to the harm that the parties to a legal dispute have caused, as well as to assist in mediating disputes before they reach the courtroom. Because of their expertise, forensic accountants are frequently used as knowledgeable advisors and expert witnesses (Bassey & Ahonkhai, 2017).

Nwaiwu, et al. (2021) state that forensic litigation support services assistance considers the analysis and reporting of issues related to assisting ongoing and impending lawsuits. In this area of knowledge, the forensic accountant may be required to assign a hypothetical value to the harm that parties to legal disputes are alleged to have inflicted and asked to assist in mediating disputes prior they reach the courtroom. Forensic accountants are typically designed to be skilled advisors and expert witnesses due to their understanding.

Onodi, et al. (2015) described the litigation services provided by forensic accountants as including: shareholders' and partnership disputes that require analysis of multiple years' worth of financial information for valuation and quantification of the matter in conflict; physical harm alleged where, for instance, economic fallout from a car accident or wrongful termination have to be quantified; business interruption and other types of insurance claims, where these assignments require a thorough examination of the accounting records; and other types of claims.

2.1.3 Fraud Prevention

Ogwiji & Lasis (2022) points out that fraud prevention combines all activities that can be utilized to decrease or

restrict the possibility of deception, making sure employees can meet their needs to relieve pressure on them that might lead to fraud, and making sure employees have no excuse to commit fraud. If a business upholds moral principles, upholds a culture of corporate honesty, evaluates possibilities, eliminates risks, reduces illegal transactions, and employs procedures for internal control, fraud can be prevented effectively.

The researchers underpinned the theories of the study on both Profession theory and fraud diamond theory. The theory of Profession helps to identify whether forensic accountancy could be considered a ‘profession’ in a traditional sense and what characteristics define a professional forensic accountant while Fraud Diamond Theory (FDT) is because of the fact that it is cheaper and sustainable to prevent fraud than to detect and prosecute fraud related matters, bearing in mind the attributes of the Fraud Diamond Theory. The use of this theory will also aid an opportunity to examine how deposit money banks formulate practical strategies in fraud prevention and investigation internally.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Forensic Investigation Services and Fraud Prevention

Madu-chima, et al (2020) carried out forensic auditing and fraud detection of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. The study examines the nexus between forensic auditing and fraud detection among Nigerian banks. The forensic auditing as independent variable proxied by fraud investigation while fraud detection as dependent variable. The survey research design and five (5) point Likert scale questionnaire were adopted for the study. The Microsoft excel and STATA 13 statistical software analysis were employed for analyzing the descriptive and inferential (lawley’s correlation). The findings show that there is a relationship between fraud investigation and fraud detection of quoted money deposit banks in Nigeria.

Okoye & Ndah (2019) focused on forensic accounting and fraud prevention in Nigeria. The study examined the relationship between forensic accounting practices and fraud prevention of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study adopted forensic accounting practices as independent variable proxied as fraud investigation practice and fraud litigation practices while fraud prevention as dependent variable. The survey research design and primary data were adopted using structured close ended questionnaire. The SPSS statistical package was used for ordinary least square (OLS) method of multiple regression analysis for the study. The result indicates that fraud investigation practices and fraud litigation practices have positive and significant effect on fraud prevention of manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Ibanichuka, et al (2020) researched on forensic accounting and quality of financial reporting of quoted banks in Nigeria. The study determines the impact of forensic accounting on quality of financial reporting for the period of ten (10) years

from 2009 to 2018 both years inclusive. The cross sectional data and ex-post facto research design were used for the study. The forensic accounting as independent variable proxied by investigative accounting service while quality of financial reporting as dependent variable proxied by accrual quality and value relevance. The study adopted panel data of linear regression using ordinary least square (OLS) and multivariate analysis technique for the analysis. The E-view software statistical package was used for the running of the analysis. The findings reveal that investigative accounting service has negative and insignificant effect on accrual quality and value relevance of quoted banks in Nigeria.

Okoye, et al. (2020) looked at forensic accounting methods for spotting labor theft in the Nigerian state of Anambra. A cross-sectional research design and targeted sample were employed in the study. A sample size of 250 people from state anti-corruption agencies, which included investigators, prosecutors, finance, accounting, and auditing professionals, made up the study population. In their study, the questionnaire served as the primary data source, and descriptive statistics and the Kruskal-Wallis test were employed to evaluate the data. The study findings that forensic accounting procedures and fraud detection in the public sector are positively and significantly associated, but there are no commonly recognized forensic investigative approaches to do so.

Ho₁: *Forensic Investigation Services (FIS) has no significant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.*

2.2.2 Forensic Litigation Support Services and Fraud Prevention

Okoye et al. (2020) adopted descriptive and inferential statistics for the study of the effect of forensic accounting evidence on litigation services in the Nigerian Judicial System using SPSS version 23 statistical software. The primary data sources were collected from Abakaliki, Ebonyi State Judiciary. The independent variable is forensic accounting evidence, proxied by forensic demonstrative evidence, forensic documentary evidence, and forensic oral evidence, while the dependent variable is litigation services. The result indicated that forensic accounting evidence (demonstrative evidence, documentary evidence, and oral evidence) has a significant effect on litigation services in the Nigerian Judicial System.

Fatoki (2021) focused on the effect of forensic accounting on financial fraud management in Nigeria Public Sector. The forensic accounting as independent variable proxied by forensic accounting and forensic litigation while financial fraud management as dependent variable. The primary source of data and descriptive survey research design were used for the study. The five (5) point Likert scale close ended questionnaire was adopted for the collection of data for analysis. The SPSS software statistical package was adopted for analyzing both descriptive statistic and multiple

regression analysis for the study. The regression result shows that forensic accounting has positive significant effect on fraud management while forensic litigation has negative insignificant effect on fraud management in Nigerian Public Sector.

Frankline, et al (2022) evaluated the impact of forensic accounting on financial reporting of selected quoted banks in Nigeria from 2004 to 2020. The forensic accounting as independent variable proxied by litigation, claims, fraud cases reported, cost of forensic investigation and non-performing loan while financial reporting as dependent variable. The quantitative research design and secondary data were used for the study. The STATA 16 was used for the analysis of descriptive statistics, panel regression analysis including Housman test, fixed effect or random effect regression model and Pearson correlation. The result shows that litigation, and cost of forensic investigation have positive insignificant effect on financial reporting but fraud cases reported has negative and insignificant effect while claim and non-performing loans have positive and significant effect on financial reporting of selected quoted banks in Nigeria.

Ismail (2020) studied forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention in the Nigerian public sector. The study employed survey design and analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the test of hypotheses. The SPSS software was also used for the running of the analysis. The study covered the ten (10) ministries from FCT Abuja. The result indicates that there is a significant correlation between forensic accounting and litigation support service in Nigerian public sector.

Nwaiwu, et al (2021) studied forensic accounting and quality of financial reporting of quoted banks in Nigeria. The study determines the effect of forensic accounting on quality of financial reporting of quoted banks in Nigeria from 2009 to 2018 both years inclusive. The forensic accounting as independent variable while quality of financial reporting as dependent variable. The ex-post facto research design and convenient sampling technique were adopted for the study. The study also employed simple regression of fixed effect for both cross sectional and time series data. The e-view version 10 was used for the running of the analysis. The findings indicate that there is positive insignificant effect of litigation services on the value relevance of quoted banks in Nigeria. Also, litigation support service has negative insignificant effect on the audit time lag of quoted banks in Nigeria.

Dada & Jimoh (2020) studied forensic accounting and financial crime in Nigerian public sector. The study examines the relationship between forensic accounting and financial crime in Lagos state public sector. The forensic accounting as independent variable measured by litigation support services while financial crime as dependent variable. The survey

= Slope or Coefficient of the independent variables and U_t = Stochastic term or error term.

research design and linear regression technique were adopted for the study. The quantitative method of data was used for the collection of structured questionnaire (close ended question) for the study. The SPSS software package was used for the analysis and the regression result shows that litigation support service has negative and significant effect on financial crimes in Lagos State public sector in Nigeria.

H0₂: *Forensic Litigation Support Services (FLSS) has no significant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.*

3. METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was used for the study because it involves the primary data which is questionnaire. The population of the study comprised all the listed deposit money banks in Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG). In Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG), the total banks under listed deposit money banks in Nigeria was twenty-four (24) as at 31st December, 2022. The sample size of the study was only fifteen (15) banks out of the total population of twenty-four (24) banks. The sampling technique used for the selection was Non-Probability or purposive sampling, i.e., convenience or accidental sampling (Onyekwelu, 2015). The five-point Likert scale questionnaire of structured closed-ended questions in the form of Strongly Agreed (5 points), Agreed (4 points), Undecided (3 points), Strongly Disagreed (2 points), and Disagreed (1 point) was adopted for data collection. The total 150 staff were issued questionnaire out of 481 staff from the selected banks but only 108 questionnaires were returned and used for the analysis. The econometric method was adopted for this study that is the ordinary least square (OLS) method of estimation that is Best Linear Unbiased Estimate (BLUE). The pool panel data generated from the fifteen (15) listed deposit money banks from selected districts in the six (6) Area Councils of the Abuja FCT, Nigeria using multiple regression analysis. The researchers also employed the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25 Statistical Software package to run the multiple regression for this study.

The study adopted the model from (Ismail, 2020 & Obiora, et al, 2022) with some modification as stated below:

$$FPV_{ij} = f(FIS_{ij}, FLSS_{ij}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$FPV_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FIS_{ij} + \beta_2 FLSS_{ij} + U_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where: FPV = Fraud Prevention, FIS = Forensic Investigation Services, FLSS = Forensic Litigation Support Services, $\sigma_0, \alpha_0, \mu_0, \beta_0$ and ρ_0 . = Intercept or constant term, $\beta_1 - \beta_2$.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables for the Study

Variables	Measurement	Sources
Fraud Prevention (FPV)	The sum of responses for the five (5) items questionnaire testing the fraud prevention in banks in Nigeria.	Obiora, et al. (2022) & Madu-Chima, et al. (2020)
Forensic Investigation Services (FIS)	The sum of responses for the five (5) items questionnaire testing the forensic investigation services in banks in Nigeria.	Madu-Chima, et al. (2020)
Forensic Litigation Support Services (FLSS)	The sum of responses for the five (5) items questionnaire testing the forensic litigation support services in banks in Nigeria.	& Madu-Chima, et al. (2020)

Source: Field work, 2024.

4. ANALYSES AND RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
FIS	108	5	25	18.80	3.701	-2.090	.233	5.686	.461
FLSS	108	14	24	20.51	2.125	-.651	.233	.230	.461
FPV	108	16	25	20.61	2.449	.260	.233	-.823	.461
Valid N (listwise)	108								

Source: Author’s Output 2024, SPSS Version 25

The table 2 above of descriptive Statistics shows that fraud prevention (FPV) has the highest mean value while forensic investigation services (FIS) has the lowest value of mean. Also, the low standard deviation of forensic litigation support services (FLSS) implies that it does not deviate so much from the mean while the standard deviation of forensic investigation services (FIS) substitution are relatively high implying much deviation from their respective means which is also reflected in the squared deviation figures. The table further indicates that the observed distribution for forensic investigation services (FIS), forensic litigation support services (FLSS) and fraud prevention (FPV) have skewness coefficients which estimate the asymmetry of the distribution

of time series data around its mean of -2.090, -0.651 and 0.260 respectively. The kurtosis coefficient, which measures how peak or flat the distribution of series for forensic investigation services (FIS), forensic litigation support services (FLSS) and fraud prevention (FPV) were 5.686, 0.230 and -0.823 respectively. The implication of the result was that the observed distribution of forensic investigation services (FIS) was normally distributed while forensic litigation support services (FLSS) and fraud prevention (FPV) were abnormally distributed. The kurtosis result indicates that forensic investigation services (FIS) has significant values while forensic litigation support services (FLSS) and fraud prevention (FPV) have insignificant values.

Table 3 Correlations

		FPV	FIS	FLSS	
Spearman's rho	FPV	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.013	.069
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.	.446	.238
		N	108	108	108
	FIS	Correlation Coefficient	.013	1.000	-.047
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.446	.	.316
		N	108	108	108
	FLSS	Correlation Coefficient	.069	-.047	1.000
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.238	.316	.
		N	108	108	108

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The table 3 of Spearman’s rho correlation indicates that forensic investigation services (FIS) and forensic litigation support services (FLSS) have positive relationship with fraud prevention (FPV). This implies that any unit increase on

forensic investigation services (FIS) and forensic litigation support services (FLSS) will result to the same unit increase on fraud prevention (FPV).

Table 4 Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
FIS	.267	108	.000	.735	108	.000
FLSS	.175	108	.000	.938	108	.000
FPV	.154	108	.000	.945	108	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The decision rule is that if the significant value of the shapiro-wilk test is greater than 0.05, the data is normal but if it is below 0.05, the data significantly deviate from a normal

distribution. Based on the above decision rule on normality test, the researcher concluded that the data is non normal because the significant value is less than 0.05.

Table 5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.483 ^a	.233	.203	2.186	.233	7.821	4	103	.000	1.978

a. Predictors: (Constant), FECS, FLSS

b. Dependent Variable: FPV

The model summary result in table 4.13 above shows that R-Squared is 23.3% of the variations in fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in Abuja FCT, Nigeria were caused by the level of forensic investigation services (FIS) and forensic litigation support services (FLSS) while 76.7% of the variation in fraud prevention (FPV) were affected by other factors outside our model. The adjusted R-Squared which indicates a figure less than 50% implies that forensic investigation services (FIS) and forensic litigation support services (FLSS) were the major determining factors of fraud

prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The Durbin-Watson Statistic is 1.978 while F-Statistic change is 7.821 at p-value of F statistic change of 0.000 at 1% level of significance. This table of model summary demonstrated how well the model fit the data of the study under consideration. As a result, it suggests that forensic investigation services and forensic litigation support services were all jointly effective measurement that had positive effect on fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Table 6 Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1 (Constant)	10.743	2.701		3.977	.000		
FIS	-.058	.059	-.088	-.977	.331	.927	1.079
FLSS	-.012	.101	-.010	-.115	.909	.965	1.036

a. Dependent Variable: FPV

Multi-collinearity is a condition where two or more predictors exhibit a high degree of linear relationship with one another. It does not exist between the explanatory variables considered in this study because all of the VIF are less than 10 and tolerance values are greater than 0.10. It is important to remember that for multi-collinearity to exist, the regressors must generate a VIF value greater than 10 and a tolerance

value less than 0.1. The findings of this study are consistent with the classical regression model's assumption that there should be no multi-collinearity among the regressors included in the model, and thus the findings revealed can be interpreted confidently.

5. DISCUSSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Ho1: *Forensic investigation services (FIS) has no significant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.*

The regression coefficient analysis table 4.43 above indicates that t-calculated of forensic investigation services (FIS) is -0.977 less than critical value of 2.0000 while P-value indicate a figure of 0.331 greater than 5% which is level of significance. This implies that forensic investigation services (FIS) has negative and insignificant effect on fraud prevention (FPV). The implication of this result shows that a unit increase in forensic investigation services will lead to the same unit decrease on fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria and vice versa. So, the researcher rejects alternate hypothesis (H_1) and accepts the null hypothesis (H_0) of hypothesis one which states that forensic investigation services (FIS) has no significant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. So, forensic investigation services are not the major determining factor for fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The finding of this study agreed with Ibanichuka, et al (2020) and Frankline, et al (2022) while in contrast with the studied by Okoye & Ndah (2019)

Ho2: *Forensic Litigation Support Services (FLSS) has no significant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.*

Table 4.43, the t-calculated of forensic litigation support services (FLSS) shows a value of $-0.115 < 2.000$ while P-value indicates a figure of 0.909 greater than 5% which is level of significance. This means that forensic litigation support services (FLSS) has negative and insignificant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The implication of this result indicates that a unit increase in forensic litigation support services will lead to the same unit decrease on fraud prevention of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria and vice versa. In this case, the researcher rejects alternate hypothesis (H_1) and accepts the null hypothesis (H_0) of hypothesis two which states that forensic litigation support services (FLSS) has no significant effect on fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. So, forensic litigation support services (FLSS) is not the major determining factor for fraud prevention (FPV) of listed deposit money banks in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The studies of Fatoki (2021); Frankline, et al (2022); Bassey & Ahonkhai (2017) and Nwaiwu, et al (2021) were in agreement with the result while Okoye, et al (2020) and Dada & Jimoh (2020) disagreed with the result.

Based on the findings above, the researchers recommend amongst others that:

1. The management should increase the use of forensic investigation services to help reduce the fraudulent activities being committed in the banks in Nigeria.

The forensic investigators should be trained professionals who must belong to the Chartered Institute of Forensics and Fraud Examiners of Nigeria (CIFCFIN), the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN), the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), or other professional bodies in Nigeria.

2. The government should provide more evidence strategies such as documental evidence, oral evidence, digital (computer) evidence and others to help support litigation activities been presented in the court by the forensic accountants. It is only registered member of professional bodies in Nigeria including the Chartered Institute of Forensics and Fraud Examiners of Nigeria (CIFCFIN) should be allowed to present such evidences in the court with the jurisdiction to hear the alleged crime of fraudulent.

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